

ALTERATION OF LAMINATE FREE EDGE STRESSES BY MOISTURE SORPTION

F.W. Crossman
and
W.S. Rothwell

Lockheed Palo Alto Research Laboratory
Palo Alto, CA 94304

A.S.D. Wang

Drexel University
Philadelphia, PA 19104

At laminate free edges, holes, or cutouts interlaminar stress concentrations develop near the free edge region as the laminate is exposed to applied mechanical loads or as internal residual stresses are altered by changing temperature or absorbed moisture conditions. Previous papers have evaluated the mechanically and thermally induced free edge stress state in finite width laminates. This paper examines the influence of absorbed moisture gradients on the interlaminar stresses near laminate free edges.